

ARE THERE WOMEN IN SENIOR LEADERSHIP POSITIONS AT PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN SERBIA?

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Abstract: *Gender inequality in academic leadership has been extensively studied worldwide. Although women have increasingly entered academia, especially at junior and mid-career level, their presence in senior leadership roles, particularly as university rectors, remains disproportionately low. In the existing literature, there is a notable lack of research focused on the gender composition of university leadership in Serbia. This paper aims to fill that gap by providing an analysis of gender representation at the highest level of academic governance, focusing on rector positions at Serbia's public universities. Using data collected from the official websites of the four largest public universities (University of Belgrade, University of Novi Sad, University of Niš, and University of Kragujevac), the study maps trends in gender distribution from the founding of these institutions to the present day. The paper aims to contribute to the discussion on gender equity in academic leadership and to offer recommendations for more inclusive governance practices in Serbian universities.*

Keywords: *gender inequality, academic leadership, university rectors, public universities, Serbia.*

When we think “leader”, we think “male” (Sinclair, 2005)

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the participation of women in higher education has increased significantly across the globe, both in terms of student enrollment and academic employment (European Commission, 2021). However, this growth has not translated equally into representation in senior academic leadership positions, where gender disparities remain a persistent issue (Fagan & Teasdale, 2021; World Economic Forum, 2024). Globally, women

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continue to face systemic, cultural and institutional barriers (Morley, 2013; European Commission, 2021; Chelan Li & Chui Ping Kam, 2021) that limit their access to executive roles such as university rectors and presidents. This phenomenon, often described as the “glass ceiling” (Bertrand, 2018), prevents women from rising to top leadership roles despite comparable qualifications. This issue is not only a matter of fairness, but also impacts institutional effectiveness and innovation capacity in higher education.

While considerable research has been conducted on gender representation in academic leadership across various regions, the situation in Serbia has received limited scholarly attention. In particular, there is a notable absence of data-driven analyses examining the gender composition of university rectors in Serbian public universities. Addressing this gap, the present study explores the extent to which women have been represented in the highest academic leadership roles at Serbia’s four largest public universities: the University of Belgrade, the University of Novi Sad, the University of Niš, and the University of Kragujevac (World Bank Group, 2022). By analyzing comprehensive institutional data, this paper provides an empirical overview of gender distribution in rector positions from the founding of these universities to 2025. The findings aim to contribute to the broader discourse on gender equity in academic leadership and provide an evidence-based perspective on leadership patterns in Serbian universities.

2. Literature review

Gender inequality in academic leadership is a globally recognized issue, with a substantial body of research documenting the persistent underrepresentation of women in senior academic and administrative roles (Kyambade et al., 2024; Maheshwari & Nayak, 2022; Chelan Li & Chui Ping Kam, 2021; Maldonado-Maldonado & Rodríguez Gómez, 2021). Despite the increasing participation of women in higher education (Galán-Muros et al., 2023), significant barriers remain to their advancement into leadership positions such as deans, vice-chancellors, and particularly university rectors, who occupy the highest executive roles within academic institutions (Morley, 2013; Glasnik Univerziteta u Beogradu, 2018).

Women remain significantly underrepresented in senior leadership positions within higher education globally. As an illustration, F. M. Cheung presents data on the extremely limited presence of women in various leadership roles across selected countries and regions (Table 1) (Cheung, 2021).

Table 1: Women in higher education leadership

Region/Country	Year	Institutional Leaders (% of Female Leaders)	Executive Leaders (% of Female Leaders)	Academic Leaders (% of Female Leaders)
Arab League	2018	6.8		
Australia	2016	25	34	34
China: “First-class universities”	2019	4.8		
Latin America	2020	18		
Pacific Rim	2018		21	25
United Kingdom	2018	29	37	31
United States	2016	30.1		

Source: Cheung, 2021.

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The data in Table 1 reflect systemic gender inequality in university leadership globally, with significant regional disparities. The United Kingdom (2018), the United States (2016), and Australia (2016) report relatively higher proportions of women in some leadership roles (institutional, executive, or academic), ranging from 30% to 37%. In contrast, regions such as the Arab League (2018) and China’s “First-class universities” (2019), show very low levels of female representation (6.8% and 4.8%, respectively), underscoring persistent gender gaps. Latin America (2020) and the Pacific Rim (2018) fall somewhere in between, reflecting uneven progress toward gender parity in higher education governance.

In 2020, Ellie Bothwell reported a modest but positive shift in the representation of women in leadership roles among the top 200 universities listed in the Times Higher Education World University Rankings (Bothwell, 2020). The proportion of female-led universities in this group rose to 19%, up from 17% three years earlier, marking the first such increase in that period. Sweden recorded the highest share of female university leaders, followed by South Africa and Spain. Other countries performing above the global average included Australia, the Netherlands, Italy, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, the United States, and France. Among these, the United States showed the most notable progress, both in the number and the proportion of institutions led by women. In contrast, Germany experienced a decline, with only one of its top universities led by a woman; down from three the previous year (Bothwell, 2020). Of the 27 countries represented among the top 200 universities, 15 had no female university leaders at all (Bothwell, 2020). Particularly striking was the absence of female presidents at leading national or public universities in Japan, South Korea, and Hong Kong, despite their high international rankings (Cheung, 2021).

Table 2 provides an overview of the top 10 universities led by women in 2020, as ranked by the Times Higher Education World University Rankings.

Table 2: Top 10 universities (Times Higher Education World University Rankings) led by women

THE World University Rank 2020	University	Country	University leader
1	University of Oxford	United Kingdom	Louise Richardson
10	Imperial College London	United Kingdom	Alice Gast
11	University of Pennsylvania	United States	Amy Gutmann
13	University of California, Berkeley	United States	Carol Christ
19	Cornell University	United States	Martha Pollack
26	University of Washington	United States	Ana Mari Cauce
27	London School of Economics and Political Science	United Kingdom	Dame Minouche Shafik
42	McGill University	Canada	Suzanne Fortier
51	University of Wisconsin-Madison	United States	Rebecca Blank
53	Brown University	United States	Christina Paxson

Note: The analysis was based on the university leader in post on 31 January 2020.

Source: Bothwell, 2020.

According to data from *She Figures 2021* (European Commission, 2021), women accounted for over 40% of academic staff across the EU in 2018. Despite this relatively balanced representation at the general academic level, significant gender disparities persist at senior academic ranks. Women held only 26.2% of grade A positions, equivalent to full professorships. Moreover, although several EU policy frameworks, such as the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, have stressed the importance of enhancing women's representation in leadership roles, the share of women heading higher education institutions remained low, at just 23.6% in 2019 (Figure 1).

According to Figure 1, the highest proportions of women among heads of higher education institutions were observed in Latvia (44.4%), Sweden (41.7%), Iceland (40.0%), Lithuania (39.0%), and Belgium (37.0%). In contrast, the lowest levels of female representation in these leadership roles were recorded in Cyprus (9.1%), Romania (11.1%), France (12.1%), Greece (16.0%), and both Czechia and Hungary, each at 17.2%. Luxembourg was excluded from the analysis, as it has only one higher education institution.

Data from the European University Association (EUA), which includes over 800 member institutions, indicate that women hold approximately 15% of rector positions. The proportion is higher for vice-rector roles, reaching nearly 30%. Notably, in 20 out of the 48 countries represented in the EUA, none of the member universities had a female rector (Nokkala, 2021).

In Eastern Europe and the Balkans, including Serbia, research on gender representation in academic leadership remains relatively limited (Mišić Andrić & Markov, 2017; Llaftiu & Shuli, 2024; Kuźelewska et al., 2024). This paper aims to fill that gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of gender representation at the highest level of academic governance, focusing on the positions of rectors at the four largest public universities in Serbia.

Although they do not directly address the issue of gender representation in senior leadership positions, it is useful to note that Slavica Manić et al. (Manić et al., 2018) highlight the undeniable presence of vertical segregation within the higher education system in Serbia. The existence of vertical segregation and the imbalance within leadership structures in the higher education sector in Serbia are also underscored by Nevena Petrušić and Dragica Vujadinović (Petrušić & Vujadinović, 2018). Among other issues, these authors draw attention to the unequal distribution of power in the selection of managerial personnel and in decision-making processes within research institutes and university faculties. They attribute this imbalance, at least in part, to authoritarian regimes and an undemocratic political culture, both of which are conducive to the reproduction of patriarchal norms within the sphere of education. As the authors argue, such regimes benefit from “the formation of heteronomous, authoritarian personality types... who will reproduce patriarchal codes and ultimately represent subservient elites readily available to serve the reproduction of authoritarian systems and social relations” (Petrušić & Vujadinović, 2018).

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Figure 1: Proportion of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector in EU in 2019

Source: European Commission, 2021.

3. Methodology, results, and discussion

This study employs secondary data to examine gender representation in senior academic leadership positions at public universities in Serbia. Data were collected from the official websites of the four largest public universities: the University of Belgrade (UB), the University of Novi Sad (UNS), the University of Niš (UNI), and the University of Kragujevac (UKG). The analysis focuses on individuals who have served as university rectors, with particular attention to gender distribution across different time periods. The dataset includes all rectors from the founding of each institution up to the year 2025 (Table 3).

Table 3. Number of rectors by universities and gender

University	Period	Total rectors	Female rectors	Male rectors	% Female rectors	% Male rectors
UB	1905-2025	43	2	41	4.65	95.35
UNS	1960-2025	19	3	16	15.79	84.21
UNI	1965-2025	15	0	15	0.00	100.00
UKG	1976-2025	13	0	13	0.00	100.00
Total	-	90	5	85	5.56	94.44

Source: Author's own

As shown in Table 3, women are significantly underrepresented in rector positions at public universities in Serbia; only 5 out of 90 rectors have been women, amounting to a mere 5.56%. The highest proportion of female rectors was recorded at the University of Novi Sad (15.79%), whereas the Universities of Niš and Kragujevac have had no female rectors to date.

To visually illustrate the extent of gender disparity, Figure 2 presents a bar chart comparing the number of male and female rectors across the four institutions.

Figure 2: Gender of university rectors in Serbia

Source: Author's own

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These findings reveal persistent gender disparities in the highest echelons of university governance. Despite the growing presence of women in academic positions over recent decades (Petrušić & Vujadinović, 2018; European Commission, 2021), clear obstacles remain when it comes to attaining top leadership roles. This pattern may be interpreted through the lens of various systemic, cultural, and institutional factors (European Commission, 2021; Morley, 2013; Chelan Li & Chui Ping Kam, 2021; Maldonado-Maldonado & Rodríguez Gómez, 2021; Ferary, 2021) that often favor men in decision-making positions.

The results of this analysis support the conclusions of numerous international studies that point to the existence of a “glass ceiling” in academia. In the Serbian context, this situation calls for further exploration of gender dynamics within higher education institutions, as well as for a strategic rethinking of approaches aimed at fostering more inclusive and equitable leadership structures.

4. Recommendations

The results of this study clearly demonstrate a persistent underrepresentation of women in the highest leadership positions at public universities in Serbia. Although this research is based on secondary data and descriptive analysis, the identified patterns point to the need for systemic interventions. To address these gender disparities and promote more inclusive leadership structures, the following recommendations are proposed (Cheung, 2021; Morley, 2013; Galán-Muros et al., 2023, Ferary, 2021; European Commission, 2021; Neehus & Volpe, 2025; European Commission, 2021a; Petrušić & Vujadinović, 2018):

- Establish transparent and gender-sensitive recruitment procedures. Selection processes for rector positions should be transparent, merit-base, and explicitly incorporate gender equality criteria. Institutional rules should be revised to include commitments to gender balance in leadership appointments.
- Develop leadership training programs for women in academia. Universities and the Ministry of Education should support the development of targeted leadership training and mentoring programs for women. These programs can help build confidence, expand professional networks, and prepare women for executive roles in academic governance.
- Strengthen institutional gender equality plans. Public universities should be required to adopt and regularly update Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), as encouraged by the European Research Area and Horizon Europe framework. These plans should include measurable goals related to leadership representation and accountability mechanism for their implementation.
- Promote cultural change within academic institutions. Beyond formal policies, universities must actively work to shift internal cultures that may implicitly favor male leadership. This includes raising awareness about unconscious bias, fostering inclusive work environments, and promoting work-life balance policies that benefit all employees regardless of gender.
- Ensure regular monitoring and public reporting on gender in leadership. Higher education institutions should systematically collect, monitor, and publish gender-disaggregated data on leadership positions. Public transparency can serve as both a

diagnostic tool and a means to hold institutions accountable for progress toward equity goals.

- Encourage national-level policy support and incentives. The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development should play a more active role by setting national guidelines for gender equity in academic leadership and offering financial or reputational incentives for institutions that demonstrate progress.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the enduring underrepresentation of women in senior academic leadership roles at public universities in Serbia. Out of 90 university rectors appointed at the four largest public institutions since their founding, only 5 have been women, an overall share of just 5.56%. While the University of Novi Sad shows a somewhat higher proportion of female leadership, the Universities of Niš and Kragujevac have never appointed a female rector. These findings reflect a broader pattern of gender inequality in higher education governance, shaped by entrenched institutional norms, limited policy interventions, and informal power structures that continue to privilege male leadership.

Addressing these disparities requires a strategic and systemic approach. Transparent recruitment processes, targeted leadership development for women, strengthened gender equality plans, and a deliberate shift in institutional culture are all essential components of meaningful change. In addition, stronger national policy support and accountability mechanisms are needed to ensure that universities not only recognize but actively eliminate barriers to women's advancement. Promoting gender equity in academic governance is not only a matter of social justice, it is also essential for fostering inclusive, innovative, and globally competitive institutions of higher education.

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IMA LI ŽENA NA NAJVIŠIM RUKOVODEĆIM POZICIJAMA NA DRŽAVNIM UNIVERZITETIMA U SRBIJI?

Rezime: Rodna neravnopravnost u akademskom liderstvu važna je tema u istraživanjima širom sveta. Iako žene sve više ulaze u akademsku sferu, posebno na početnim i srednjim nivoima karijere, njihova prisutnost na najvišim rukovodećim pozicijama, naročito u ulozi rektorki, i dalje je nesrazmerno mala. U postojećoj literaturi uočava se nedostatak istraživanja koja se fokusiraju na rodni sastav univerzitetskog rukovodstva u Srbiji. Ovaj rad ima za cilj da doprinese popunjavanju te praznine pružajući analizu rodne zastupljenosti na najvišem nivou akademskog liderstva, s posebnim fokusom na pozicije rektora na državnim univerzitetima u Srbiji. Korišćenjem podataka prikupljenih sa zvaničnih internet stranica četiri najveća državna univerziteta (Univerzitet u Beogradu, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Univerzitet u Nišu i Univerzitet u Kragujevcu), istraživanje mapira trendove u rodnoj raspodeli najviše liderske pozicije od osnivanja ovih institucija do danas. Rad ima za cilj da doprinese raspravi o rodnoj ravnopravnosti u akademskom liderstvu i da ponudi preporuke za inkluzivnije prakse upravljanja na univerzitetima u Srbiji.

Ključne reči: rodna nejednakost, akademsko liderstvo, rektori univerziteta, državni univerziteti, Srbija.